

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 5.2

Definition of citizen-observed and authoritative data collection requirements for LandSense demonstration cases

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Short Description:
Data collection requirements relevant for LandSense pilots were identified and described. Definitions to ensure that data acquired through LandSense pilots suits its purpose and follows the legal constrains were elaborated. LandSense pilots data collection flow is outlined, specific elements relevant to quality assessment and data capture are highlighted. Considerations on scientific, commercial and governmental application of LandSense data collection requirements were provided.
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List of Acronyms and meaning

ATKIS	Topographisch-Kartographische Informationssystem - German federal land use system
BLI	BirdLife International - non-governmental wildlife conservation organization
CO	Citizen observatory - community-based monitoring systems e.g. for the environment or other phenomena of interest
CS	Citizen science - CO framed as a credible source to address scientific questions
CHEI	City of Heidelberg - specific European administrative unit
CIR	Contributors interpretation redundancy - different citizens, by design deliberately interpreting same phenomena e.g. usually for quality assurance
DCR	Data collection requirement - important features and data input by a citizen (user) to solve and address a specific citizen science application
EO	Earth observation - measuring spectral properties from a distance
eDCR	Essential data collection requirements - mandatory DCR e.g. legally mandatory
EU	European Union - super national political and economic union
GDPR	General data protection regulation - set of EU regulations to ensure digital user privacy
GPS	Global positioning system - space borne infrastructure that enables position determination anywhere on earth
IBA	Important bird and biodiversity areas - BLI focused areas of interest e.g. areas particularly vulnerable or threatened regarding wildlife conservation
IGN	Institut Géographique National - French administrative establishment to produce and maintain spatial information
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature - important organization that gathers, advocates and analyses data regarding nature conservation
LULC	Land use and land cover - anthropogenic usage of land and biogeochemical cover of land
LEP	LandSense engagement platform - confluence space of LandSense pilots and services
OSM	OpenStreetMap - collaborative free editable map of the world
QA	Quality assurance - system of references, checks and algorithms that determine the quality of data
QAC	Quality assurance and control - control mechanisms of QA e.g. a DCR is QA control mechanism
rDCR	Recommended data collection requirements - DCR that leverages the impact of a citizen observatory e.g. improves its quality
RT	Real time - capacity to capture phenomena as they occur
UHEI	University of Heidelberg - geoinformation department of a university
UBA	Umweltbundesamt Wien - independent governmental spin off performing environment analysis
UUID	Universally unique identifier - distinct digital identity
VHR	Very high resolution - spatial resolution <1m EO data
VU	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam - environment department of a university

Executive Summary

This document describes the data collection requirements for the pilot cases within the LandSense Citizen Observatory. Expectations from governance, science and commercial sector were outlined and considered. For each LandSense pilot, simple and relevant data collection requirements were presented, fostered and summarized. Data flows workings are provided for each pilot. Data collection requirements and related critical quality assessment procedures are highlighted and defined.

1 Introduction

Data collection requirements (DCR)s form the first stage of the quality assurance (QA) processes for data collected within the LandSense Citizen Observatory. Weak DCRs may result in poorly collected or low-quality citizen-observational data, while strong DCRs can generate meaningful data to drive evidence-based decision making. DCRs reflect a citizen observatory (CO) project gravity to purpose and ensure data fitness for quality assurance and control (QAC) tool provided by the LandSense engagement platform (LEP). Execution of quality estimation for quality control (QC) requires that data is collected in certain ways. Since different quality estimators and their requirements call for different DCRs, we defined two categories of DCR:

- **Essential data collection requirements** (eDCR)s are mandatory for any citizen observation and must be executed, they are: Privacy of individuals and public on any captured photo, user privacy for registered contributors, usage of universally unique identifier (UUID)s and time stamps for any data collected.
- **Recommended data collection requirements** (rDCR)s are dependent on the data captured within a LandSense pilot activity. For example, a minimum amount of observations necessary to describe a phenomenon or a minimum global positioning system (GPS) accuracy. Additional rDCRs include: validity of digitized polygons, photo illumination validity, position validity and validity of sampling population and sampling design. In contrast to eDCRs, rDCRs are not strictly mandatory but aimed to promote data quality.

The DCRs described here serve as data capture filter (for instance a minimum proximity of a contributor to the feature investigated) or may identify that a campaign requires additional data to fulfil its purpose (for instance to meet statistical requirements that allow a valid data interpretation of the campaign). D5.1 provided an overview of quality items of potential relevance for LandSense pilots and D2.2 stated their ambitions and implementation strategy. LandSense pilots vary by purpose and application and so does the DCRs types of data captured. Nonetheless, there are generic elements that allow redundant usage of a single DCR type by different pilots.

Since LandSense requires conflation of political, scientific and industrial arenas, DCRs must reflect the dynamics and requirements connecting them. Figure 1 outlines the relevant arenas and depicts their relation to LandSense pilots. LandSense Urban Landscapes Dynamics theme is primarily targeted for governmental usage such as planning and management of urban life. There, DCR requirements are formulated by stakeholder requirements, which are: up to date land use information systems (Institut Géographique National (IGN) mapper and OpenStreetMap (OSM) landuse and to promote recreational value of green spaces (Frei.Raum.Netz/CityOasis and Green Spaces NL). Agricultural land use and forest and habitat monitoring themes are embraced by industrial applications directly aiming for commercial application and therefore a necessity for efficiency and lean deployment. The purpose of the Industrial arena is to create and address user needs. Science encourages involvement of novel methods and technologies relevant to address good practices and objective quantification of fitness for purpose. For the sake of LandSense and any successful citizen science (CS) initiative the three arenas need to benefit from each other.

Governance and industry together define LandSense ambitions. Industry and science transfer and provide services and knowledge to each other. Science and governance ensure that LandSense data is captured in such a fashion that fitness for purpose is ensured. As a result, LandSense DCR must be efficient and practical (dictated by industry) fulfil governance stakeholder requirements such as ensuring citizen privacy and ensure scientific standards and good practices. Although the different LandSense pilots within their themes target specific arenas of society (governance, science and industry) ideally, they should produce sound data for each arena. For instance, beyond the practical usage of land use for governmental planning activities, science might stimulate research on land use forecasting and industry might develop commercialisation, selling land use CO devices/systems also to non-European Union (EU) countries.

The agricultural crop support system of INOSENS, which is currently intended to promote commercial value of farms can find various extensions, both in scale and application as potential looms. The pilot can find future application for governmental subvention regulation for specific crops and within science to forecast crop yields or issue alarms exposing vulnerabilities of specific crop types in the light of upcoming climate change intensification. LandSense and CS DCRs need to accommodate the needs of the different arenas, to support their growth.

Failure to meet requirements from these three arenas can result in disapproval of data collected by LandSense or any CS, either by stakeholders or the scientific community. Eroding consolidated scientific practices is prohibitive just like failure to understand needs defined by stakeholders. Thus, meeting their requirements is an essential necessity for LandSense to qualify as validated CS activity. LandSense acknowledges both: consolidated scientific standards and legislation practice of the EU. Our DCRs combined realities of political necessities (privacy of individual), consolidated scientific standards, format standards (evolved good practices within the scientific community) and economic opportunities in the form of a market (shared usage of services through the LEP).

Figure 1 Each circle resembles an import arena of society that was accommodated within the LandSense data collection requirements; used colours and line types do not resemble specific meaning other than aesthetics

Table 1 serves as an overview of the current state of LandSense pilots in respect to their application, dependencies and added value they may generate. The first column provides an overview of the LandSense themes and subsequently their relation to the pilots, applications and institutions. The dependencies column resemble existing or ongoing data streams vital for the pilot’s functionality. City of Heidelberg (OSMlanduse) and Toulouse (IGN Paysages) are both dependent on OSM, where City of Heidelberg additionally relies on the functionalities of LACO-wiki and availability of Sentinel 2 data or better. City of Vienna (Frei.Raum.Netz/City Oasis) and Amsterdam (Green Space NL) relied on FotoQuest Go technology and input of green spaces location as they can be provided by the respective municipalities. Serbia (CropSupport) relies on Sentinel 2 data and ideally up to date very high-resolution data to reliably identify land parcels. Indonesia and Spain’s Natura Alert app relies on the LandSense change detector service and marked location of Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBA).

Table 1 LandSense pilots overview

Theme	Pilot	Application(s)	Institution	Dependencies	Added value
Urban Landscape Dynamics	City of Heidelberg	OSMlanduse validation (Quality estimation of CO land use)	University of Heidelberg (UHEI) and City of Heidelberg (CHEI)	OpenStreetMap (OSM), Up-to-date Sentinel2 or better and laco-wiki.net	Identification of CO land use suited for municipality use
	City of Toulouse and surrounding areas	IGN mapper (Update, Improvement and enrichment of LULC 2013/16)	Institut géographique national (IGN)	OpenStreetMap (OSM), French land use and land cover (LULC) 2013 data and very high resolution (VHR) data (Bing google earth)	
	City of Vienna	Frei.Raum.Netz (CityOasis) (human interaction green spaces assessment)	Umweltbundesamt (UBA) Wien, MA18 Stadtentwicklung und Stadtplanung	FotoQuest Go technology and local green spaces layer	Robust collection of green space perception as information layer for municipality green space planning
	City of Amsterdam	Green Space NL (human interaction green spaces assessment)	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU)		

Agricultural Land Use	Serbia	CropSupport (field crop management)	INOSENS	Up to data VHR data (e.g. Bing Google earth or Sentinel2)	Online farm management tool including crop fruit monitor
Forest and Habitat Monitoring	Spain	Natura Alert app (species occurrence collection)	Bird Life International (BLI)	Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBA) locations	Knowledge of threats to biodiversity
	Indonesia			Change detector (LandSense service) for deforestation	Knowledge of threats to biodiversity and deforestation occurrence

Chapter two provided an overview of data types captured by LandSense pilots revealing the flow of information, chain of events and dependencies for each of them. Chapter three outlines the DCRs and offers relevant literature and considerations covering definitions and necessities provided by the Geoinformatics, CS and earth observation (EO) scientific communities.

To satisfy principles of scientific ethics, application for purpose and the respect for user privacy we formulated three CO DCR axioms:

- Scaling axiom - data provided and captured should stimulate conflation with other data and cooperation of stakeholders and users
- Purpose axiom - captured data should be accurate enough to support the intention of the pilot and should not mislead users and data evaluation
- Privacy axiom – data collected should acknowledge contributor’s privacy

2 LandSense data collection requirements (DCRs)

DCRs are the first stage of LandSense quality assurance (QA) and are required for the implementation of the quality assurance and control (QAC) services offered within the LEP. Table 2 outlines seven DCRs. Each pilot resembles its own set of DCRs. For instance, IGMmapper and CropSupport are the only pilots where polygons are collected, ensuring a valid polygon topology (e.g. non-overlapping polygons) is just applicable for those two. DCRs are linked to feedback mechanisms, requiring the contributor or the LandSense campaign manager to act upon.

Polygon validity (PV) refers to overlapping polygons and sliver polygon, requiring the LEP QAC polygon topology check (section 3.1). Implementation is handled in real time (RT) thus at the very moment a polygon is drawn and conflicting with another it either cannot be finished, until conflicting nodes are altered or must be auto resolved by a computer. **Photos privacy validity (PP)** is an essential (mandatory) DCR. The LEP QAC photo analysis machine learning (see D5.3) based pattern recognition identifies in near real time (NRT) data in such a way that privacy of individuals present in the photo is preserved (e.g. blurring of faces). The same QAC service provides an estimate of the captured **photo illumination validity (PI)**. If too dark or bright, content re-capture or automatic correction is suggested. **Position validity (PO)** relies on the QAC concerned about GPS accuracy. PV DCR covers both, minimum required GPS accuracy and proximity requirements of contributions in case of guided campaign design. Guided campaign design allows application of sampling design which subdivides in **sampling population (SP)** and **sampling strata (SS)**. SP is of importance for the change detection service and the OSMLanduse application. Their thematic area estimations require a sampling sizes that supports the calculation of confidence interval and desirably narrow confidence intervals. A properly sized SP is mandatory for the QAC service of categorical accuracy to provide reliable results. Here thematic, spatial thematic and temporal accuracy are combined by the term categorical accuracy for the respective QAC service as they describe similar concepts. Determination if the timing of an event was captured appropriately was also related to these accuracy measures.

SS stratification of samples is required for contributor cross check to calculate contributor's agreement (section 3.5) a novel quality measure for CO. **User privacy (UP)** DCR type is shared with information provided by the contributor's device and profile. Device type, operating system version and time stamps connected to data entries are necessary to collect for QAC. It is important that this information is collected in such a way that the identity of a contributor can be anonymized (section 0). There is no DCR feedback linked to this data because users need to provide this information before participating a campaign. Some LandSense pilots require additional information besides standard login. For instance, Greenspaces NL and Frei.Raum.Netz (CityOasis) requires additional information about a contributor's affinity to nature and must ensure user privacy for this sensitive data.

DCR feedback towards the contributor can appear in real time (RT) and near real time (NRT) where post campaign (PC) feedback is visible to the LandSense campaign manager and will only affect a contributor indirectly (e.g. as a result of another campaign planning or an adjusted campaign). Measures related to post campaign are usually complex and require the related entirety population of campaign content captured. First, RT feedback is provided as the data is captured. For instance, a location can only be captured if within

a well-defined proximity of a guided location and of a specific minimum GPS accuracy. Thus, RT quality checks occur directly on the smartphone and do not require a connection to a remote host. Second, in contrast to RT near real time (NRT) quality check requires communication with a LandSense service which can alter content automatically, for instance blurring out faces or car license plates to ensure privacy. Finally, post campaign (PC) DCR is done when a data collection campaign is finished. All data collected during the campaign is used to draw conclusions about its use, for instance the comparison of different user performances or descriptive statistics of entire populations of campaign data. While RT and NRT are automated and optimally influence the contributor to provide high quality data, PC requires further assessment and actions by a LandSense operator. As a result, PC can identify that a campaign requires additional data to serve the purpose of the pilot (i.e. additional data or sampling is required to reach scientifically robust conclusions).

DCR pilot applicability of LandSense data capture requirements for the specific pilots is shown in the third column and explained in detail across sections 2.1- 2.5.

Table 2 LandSense data capture requirements (DCR) frame work; ✓ indicates applicability; * includes Vienna and Amsterdam; ** includes Spain and Indonesia

DCR type Acronym / Name	DCR categories	Required LEP quality assurance and control (QAC) items	DCR feedback			DCR pilot applicability				
			Real time (RT)	Near real time (NRT)	Post campaign (PC)	OSM Landuse guided	IGN Mapper opportunistic	Crop Support opportunistic	Green Spaces* guided	Natura Alert** opportunistic
PV / Polygon validity	recommended	Polygon topology check	✓				✓	✓		
PP / Photo privacy validity	essential	Photo analysis		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
PI / Photo Illumination validity	recommended									
PO / Position validity	recommended	Position accuracy	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓
SP / sampling population	recommended	Categorical accuracy			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
SS / sampling strata	recommended	Contributors Agreement				✓			✓	
UP / user privacy, time stamp, device details	essential	UUID/GDPR compliance	✓							

2.1 City of Heidelberg OSMLanduse

The objective of Heidelberg University (UHEI) and City (CHEI) pilot is the evaluation of citizen-generated land use maps to identify their suitability for municipality land management usage. Subsection 2.1.1 provides a schematic overview and DCR applicability of the pilot. Subsection 2.1.2 provides details on existing requirements relevant to the pilot DCR expressed by stakeholders and identified through literature. Subsection 2.1.3 provides an overview of the data collected and shows their link to the DCR of the pilot.

2.1.1 Pilot schematic outline and DCR applicability

Land use maps generated rely on OpenStreetMap (OSM) and Sentinel 2 data. Instead of Sentinel 2 very VHR data (<1m) is required and envisioned for Heidelberg and Toulouse. It can be argued that availability of VHR data is a DCR for this pilot. Since the selection of EO data is not an active choice of a contributor it was not listed as CO DCR. Guided validation campaigns are designed on laco-wiki.net where contributors provide a truthful response of the land use using VHR EO data as guidance. Contributors are free to select any of the land use classes shown in Table 3, to the best of their knowledge. Typically, a validation campaign consists of hundreds of points where one after another is exposed for interpretation by a single or multiple contributors.

For this pilot three DCRs exist. Applicable DCRs, type of DCR, the related DCR axiom and potential purpose in relation to LEP QAC is listed below:

- Sufficient sampling population (SP) size is a recommended DCR (rDCR) necessary for high confidence thematic accuracy estimates (section 3.4) and is related to the purpose axiom because it allows meaningful interpretation of the data.

Before the campaign a sufficient amount of reference points must be made available (sampling design) to ensure necessary statistical robustness of results generated. A lack of reference points results in low confidence of class accuracy estimation, sufficient reference points enable accuracy estimates with high confidence (Olofsson et al., 2014) (section 3.4). As a result, the LandSense campaign manager must ensure sufficient participation. Contributors do require a minimum understanding of EO image interpretation, which is delivered in the form of training (i.e. tutorial and videos) before the mapping activity.

- Sampling stratification (SS) is a rDCR which enables identification of inappropriate contributions (section 3.4) and is related to the scaling axiom because it ensures that the results achieved are comparable for other sites. It is also related to the purpose axiom as it provides a basis to create reliable results worth of decision-oriented interpretation.

Guided campaign design allows calculation of contributor agreement realized by Scot's Pi. Contributors input repeatedly in disparity with the majority vote are removed from the campaign (section 3.5). Additionally, a fraction of 10% of contributors input is cross checked by a LandSense expert to estimate the quality of the reference data set created by the volunteers.

- User privacy, time stamp, device details (UP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and is related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

This pilot does not collect any additional data about contributors other than those required by the LandSense federation login.

Figure 2 UHEI pilot data dependencies and flow of data capture to create evaluated OSM Land use map; *legend construction of land use is flexible currently is CORINE; ** Currently Landsat and Sentinel 2 is used very high resolution (VHR) data is envisioned

2.1.2 Existing requirements

Vermessungsamt Heidelberg (survey department Heidelberg) and Rhein-Neckar-Kreis (Heidelberg county) reported that current land use data (Amtliche Topographisch-Kartographische Informationssystem (ATKIS)) thematic accuracy is not satisfactory (~70%). A stated reason was that ATKIS is updated on-demand rather than systematically. Technically, it's a spatially explicit vector data container of sporadically updated land use information. Improved land use information is relevant for both administrative entities which shall be:

- Up to date (as defined by stakeholder city of Heidelberg)
- minimum spatial resolution <1m (defined by stakeholder City of Heidelberg)
- systematic accuracy assessment acknowledging statistical principles (Strahler et al., 2006)
- accuracy higher than 70% (Anderson et al. (1976) recommends 85%)

In LandSense this is addressed by creating an up to date OSM based land use map of the most recent OSM. The UHEI validation campaigns, hosted on laco-wiki.net, accommodate the municipalities request for systematic accuracy assessment of the CO produced maps.

2.1.3 Data collection catalogue

Table 3 shows data collected for this pilot and the relation to the DCRs. Data for this pilot is currently exclusively collected via a web application but can also be collected using a mobile device. For each location, the contributor chooses in campaign webform from 12 land use classes (following Corine land cover legend)

(Schultz et al., 2017). For this pilot the campaign manager must consider sampling design in such a way that the production of accurate area estimations is possible (Card, 1982).

Table 3 Data collection catalogue City of Heidelberg OSMLanduse;* classes shown follow CORINE nomenclature

Collection domain	Categories	DCR and related quality measure
Web – choice of 12 Land use classes via laco-wiki.net	*11 urban fabric; 12 industrial, commercial and transport units; 13 mine dump and construction sites; 14 artificial non-agricultural areas; 21 arable land; 22 permanent crops; 23 pastures; 31 forests; 32 shrubs and herbaceous vegetation; 33 open spaces with little or no vegetation; 41 inland wetlands; 50 water bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SP - for each class sufficient amount of collected data to calculate confident thematic accuracy (section 3.4) • SS - stratification of samples to cross check users (section 3.5)
login	login to LandSense federation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UP - user privacy (section 0)

2.2 City of Vienna – Frei.Raum.Netz (City Oasis) / City of Amsterdam GreenSpacesNL

The objective of the city of Vienna and Amsterdam pilots is to understand citizen perception of green/open spaces for future municipality green space planning activities. A survey of green space effects and determination of its recreational value can improve the quality of life for a city and thus improve its overall value in comparison to other cities. Subsection 2.2.1 provides a schematic overview and DCR applicability of the pilot. Subsection 2.2.2 provides details on existing requirements relevant to the pilot DCR expressed by stakeholders and identified through literature. Subsection 2.2.3 provides an overview of the data collected and shows their link to the DCR of the pilot.

2.2.1 Pilot schematic outline and DCR applicability

Outcomes from this pilot are “emotional” maps regarding the perception of green spaces by citizens. Data is collected exclusively via smart phone where Google Earth imagery provides a background for orientation of contributors while navigating towards locations defined by the guided campaign design. To join the pilot, contributors currently need to provide personal information regarding their gender, age and nature affinity. Three data collection requirements apply coupled with quality constraints realized in real and near-real time, also two additional post-processing quality check procedures apply. First, as a proximity constraint, the data must be captured at least 30m near the location suggested by the guided campaign design (campaign manager), hence data collection is restricted until proximity is achieved. Feedback regarding the positional accuracy proximity constraint is provided in real time to the contributor. Second, a VHR EO image is needed as a background layer to aid navigation of the contributor. As Google Earth imagery is composed of VHR data, no requirements other than that applies (e.g. VHR data from specific moment in time can be used as an alternative). This contrasts with other pilots, which might not necessarily require VHR data but demand

timely (up to date) EO data (UHEI, Birdlife and INOSENS pilots), such as the latest Sentinel 2 data. Third, as applicable for all LandSense pilots captured photos, image content of faces and car plate signs is blurred in NRT by communication with a LandSense services to preserve privacy of the public. Finally, photo brightness is checked on a LandSense server in NRT it was not decided yet if the user is given the chance to recapture the photo.

The two following DCRs of the pilot contain quantitatively collected data. Firstly, for the question and secondly for multiple choice section. DCR must provide means to enable quality checks related to the input selection of contributors and aim to remove faulty contributions. In contrast to other LandSense pilots, UBA mainly collects data regarding user's feelings or in other words individually subjective data, thus comparison to reference data is impossible. However, targeted objective key questions (reference questions) can be used to evaluate soundness of a user's contribution for the respective point. For instance, "How many trees do you see?" is an objective question where contributors at the same location should arrive at the same conclusion. Since UBA's campaign design is guided, multiple contributors can be sent to the same location without knowledge from another (blind sampling). As such, the Contributor agreement quality check is of special importance for UBA pilot.

For this pilot five DCRs exist. Applicable DCRs, type of DCR, the related DCR axiom and potential purpose in relation to LEP QAC is listed below:

- Position validity (PO) is a recommended DCR (rDCR) providing estimates of position accuracy of user contributions (section 3.3) and related to the purpose axiom because it allows meaningful interpretation of the data.

Currently the user must be within the proximity of 30m of the guided feature (location of green space). For this pilot internal GPS accuracy is not further defined yet. The 30m proximity constrain of the contribution was based on internal decisions within UBA.

- Sampling stratification (SS) is a rDCR which enables identification of inappropriate contributions (section 3.4) and is related to the scaling axiom because it ensures that the results achieved are comparable for other sites. It is also related to the purpose axiom as it provides a basis to create reliable results worth of decision-oriented interpretation.

Guided campaign design allows calculation of contributor agreement realized by Scot's Pi. Contributors input repeatedly in disparity with the majority vote are removed from the campaign (section 3.5). For Green Spaces NL a sampling stratification where locations should be visited at least 5 times by different interpreters is recommended as it is currently the only mean to check reliability of the contributing users.

- Photo privacy validity (PP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and photo analysis (section 3.2). It is related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

Although cities green spaces are public areas captured photo content must be screened for the sake of respecting privacy of individuals.

- Photo illumination validity (PI) is an rDCR ensuring interpretation of captured photos (section 3.2) and is related to the purpose axiom to ensure meaningful interpretation of the photo.

Identification of green spaces and potential further conclusions may be derived from the pictures at a later stage of the project. Thus, photos should be available in such a quality allowing interpretation.

- User privacy, time stamp, device details (UP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

Any data captured within LEP must ensure user privacy and its rigorous enforcement, especially captured data about age, gender and names are highly sensitive information.

Figure 3 UBA pilot data dependencies and flow of data capture to create emotional map of green spaces; * as is may be changed of anonymized; ** blind revisit of multiple users for later contributors agreement calculation; *** minimum proximity to guided location must be <30m

2.2.2 Existing requirements

The City of Vienna is interested in subjective perception of green/open spaces for steering emotion-based city planning decisions. Frei.Raum.Netz (CityOasis) provides the chance to capture emotions and observations in a guided and systematic fashion. Thus far, such data and the mode of data capture is novel for the municipality of Vienna city planning section. The municipalities require “emotional maps” providing conclusions as to which recreational green spaces are of valuable to the citizens (cities inhabitants). Evaluation of the “emotional maps” provides a novel planning and communication device centred around the perception of the cities inhabitants.

Upscaling is possible for areas and cities with a critical mass of locals willing to contribute to the development of their green areas. Thus far, a similar pilot is performed in Amsterdam. Due to the readiness of students and young people to contribute via smartphones while enjoying green spaces, the pilot can be applied in any major European city via a local authority or a university.

2.2.3 Data collection catalogue

Table 4 shows data collected for this pilot and the relation to the DCRs. Besides LandSense federation login an extended login where personal data is requested is required for participation. Data for this pilot is exclusively collected via a mobile application. The additional data is linked to the observations to understand responses of green spaces for different age groups and the individual’s affinity to nature. GPS location is required to match the observation to the related greenspace and ensure that contributor is within proximity. Although the contributors can choose from different occupancies no DCR is applicable because currently there is no means to validate this input. Thus, occupations shall be interpreted with a grain of salt. The measurement of observed features such as butterflies cannot be validated however the amount of trees present can be validated. A user which does repeatedly provide falsely information about objective amounts of trees present in comparison to the other users (section 3.5) may also not be trusted for their observation of butterflies and as a result be removed from the analysis. For reliable estimation of agreement measure 5 observations shall be made for the same location from different contributors. Captured photo material is subjected to image checks regarding privacy and lightning.

Table 4 Data collection catalogue Green spaces, shown here for Frei.Raum.Netz (City Oasis) Vienna; * other than trees categories are subjective

Collection domain	Categories	DCR and related Quality measure
Mobile – GPS position	x/y coordinates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PO – minimum distances to guided location <30m (section 3.3)
	distance to guided location	
Mobile – count features from 6 categories	*mood, quietness, safety, cleanliness, attractiveness, functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SS - stratification of samples to cross check users (section 3.5)
Mobile – choice of 7 activities	*standing, sitting, lying (e.g. prone), playing, walking, sports, other activity	No DCR applicable
Mobile - photos	4 photos in cardinal directions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PP – blurry out faces and car plate signs (sections 3.2 and 0) • PI – ensure proper illumination (section 3.2)

login	Login to LandSense federation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UP - User privacy (section 0)
Extended profile – 3 items	Gender, Age, Nature affinity	

2.3 City of Toulouse – IGN mapper

The objective of the IGN-France-led pilot is to update and improve land use information for the city of Toulouse. Activities in the pilot include improving existing land use information of 2013, updating land use that changed in 2016 and detailing thematic information of building usage. Subsection 2.1.1 provides a schematic overview and DCR applicability of the pilot. Subsection 2.1.2 provides details on existing requirements relevant to the pilot DCR expressed by stakeholders and identified through literature. Subsection 2.1.3 provides an overview of the data collected and shows their link to the DCR of the pilot.

2.3.1 Pilot schematic outline and DCR applicability

The IGN pilot is composed of three elements and data is captured in both opportunistic and guided campaigns. First, a land use and land cover (LULC) improvement data of the year 2013. Second, a LULC data for updating the LULC 2013 database to 2016 using recent EO data. Thirdly, a thematic enrichment of building features of the LULC building data set. Data flow from contributor and existing data sources towards an improved LULC 2013 map is shown in Figure 4. Data collection requirement is limited to correctly drawn polygons (overlap and sliver) and user feedback is provided in real time. Thematic correctness and appropriate timing of provided LULC information is subject to post campaign evaluation.

- Sufficient sampling population (SP) size is a recommended DCR (rDCR) necessary for high confidence thematic accuracy estimates (section 3.4) and related to the purpose axiom because it allows meaningful interpretation of the data.

The DCR is only applicable for the guided campaign designs available for update LULC 2016 and enriching building information. Both themes can be subjected to thematic accuracy assessment which requires application standard accuracy assessment procedures and a critical mass of contributions. The DCR is not applicable when contribution numbers are high (>500 contributions).

- Sampling stratification (SS) is a rDCR which enables identification of inappropriate contributions (section 3.4) and is related to the scaling axiom because it ensures that the results achieved are comparable for other sites. It is also related to the purpose axiom as it provides a basis to create reliable results worth of decision-oriented interpretation.

The DCR is only applicable for the guided campaign designs available for update LULC 2016 and enriching building information. It is only applicable if enough contributors participate.

- Photo privacy validity (PP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and photo analysis 3.2. It is related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

Photos of buildings might contain sensitive material of residents and vehicles parked in their proximity. In contrast to the other pilots these photos might be filled with objects that require anonymization.

- Photo illumination validity (PI) is an rDCR ensuring interpretation of captured photos (section 3.2) and is related to the purpose axiom to ensure meaningful interpretation of the photo.

Identification of the respective land use or building investigated requires appropriate lighting conditions. Ideally the captured photo shall allow interpretation of the building height and the number of involved stories.

- Position validity (PO) is a recommended DCR (rDCR) providing estimates of position accuracy of user contributions (section 3.3) and related to the purpose axiom because it allows meaningful interpretation of the data.

Currently no IGN Mapper specific restrictions apply other than the capture of the GPS coordinates and the location error.

- Polygon validity (PV) is a recommended DCR (rDCR) (section 3.1) and is related to the purpose axiom ensuring that covered areas can be derived correctly. It is also related to the scaling axiom because polygons free of overlaps and splinters can be compared to others and can find conflation in other CO or OSM data bases.

IGN Mapper provides digitizing capabilities in a webform particularly to map buildings.

- User privacy, time stamp, device details (UP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

This pilot does not collect any additional data about contributors other than those required by the LandSense federation login

Figure 4 IGN pilot data dependencies and flow of data capture to create improved LULC 2013; provide voluntarily: gender, age, profession and institution

The second IGN pilot related to LULC update 2016 allows users to contribute via mobile phone (guided) and web (opportunistic), thus data collection requirements are more extensive in comparison to the first theme. Figure 5 shows the data flow and capture requirements related to the theme. The Web based data collection requirements are same as for the LULC 2013 theme. Mobile-based data capture does not offer to draw polygons but allows thematic data capture and photos as a device to collect evidence of the provided categorical input. There are no specific positional accuracy requirements. Image content of faces and car license plates are blurred in NRT by communication with a LandSense server to preserve privacy of the public. Finally, photo brightness is checked on a LandSense server in NRT. Post campaign QA does apply, but is not related to the moment of data capture.

Figure 5 IGN pilot data dependencies and flow of data capture to create updated LULC 2016; provide voluntarily: gender, age, profession and institution

Third, IGN data flow is shown in Figure 6. Collection requirements are similar as for the LULC 2016 theme (previous section) but in contrast require fewer quality checks for post processing as only thematic information requires evaluation and not time of data acquisition.

Figure 6 IGN pilot data dependencies and flow of data capture to enrich building information with thematically

2.3.2 Existing requirements

Update, improvement and enrichment of thematic land use data is of importance for municipality planning. Professional surveys can incur high costs, which may be reduced when approaches using CO are integrated. Resources saved for update and improvement of IGN land use data sets can be allocated elsewhere, for instance in building comprehensive database and data management system to decide on complex infrastructure planning. Upscaling possibilities are possible for any municipality and city planning department willing to dedicate the necessary resources for installment and maintenance. Alternatively, the pilot infrastructure can be managed centrally, with one expert managing various cities simultaneously. Critical aspects regarding upscaling is the mobilization of contributors.

2.3.3 Data collection catalogue

Table 5 shows data collected for this pilot and the relation to the DCRs. LandSense federation login is required for participation of the mobile and web app. This pilot is composed of three pilots combined under a land use theme. The LULC 2013 improvement theme is exclusively accessed via a web application form where contributors can update polygons and land use of existing entities using one of the 17 IGN classes. No DCR other than a valid polygon expression and response on land use is required. Because campaign design is opportunistic, no cross check among other contributors can be performed. Area estimates about accuracy of improved LULC 2013 is also restricted under the current pilot implementation. LULC 2016 update allows both guided and opportunistic campaign design which allows for contributor agreement and area accuracy estimates of changed land user of appropriate sampling design (section 3.4) and stratification (section 3.5) is applied. Web and Mobile contributions are both possible where for mobile based contributions no restrictions in terms of GPS accuracy apply, captured photos are subjected to image analysis to ensure privacy of individuals and appropriate lightning for image interpretation. The building theme includes capture of GPS coordinates and selection of primary and secondary function of the building as well as the number of stories.

Table 5 Data collection catalogue IGN mapper, land use legend follows IGN classification scheme

Collection domain	Categories	DCR and related Quality measure
Web/Mobile - choice of 17 Land use classes via Paysages mobile app or IGN online tool (mobile app currently features free entry)	US1.1 Agriculture, US1.2 Sylviculture (Forest), US1.3 Activités d'extraction (Mining), US1.4 Pêche et Aquaculture (Fishing and Aquaculture) US1.5 Autres productions primaires (Other primary productions), US235 Production secondaire, tertiaire et us residential (Secondary and tertiary production and residential areas), US4.1.1 Réseaux routiers (Road Networks), US4.1.2 Réseaux ferrés (Railway networks), US4.1.3 Réseaux aériens (Air networks), US4.1.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SP - for each class sufficient amount of collected data to calculate confident thematic accuracy (section 3.4) • SS - stratification of samples to

	Réseaux de voies navigables (Inland waterway networks), US4.1.5 Autres réseaux de transport (Other transport networks), US4.2 Services, logistiques et stockage (Services, logistics and storage), US4.3 Reseaux d'utilité publique (Public utility networks), US6.1 Zones en transition (Transition Zones), US6.2 Zones abandonnées (Abandoned areas), sans usage (no usage) US6.4 Usage incoma (income generating)	cross check users (section 3.5)
Mobile/Web – 2 choice of usage and 1 numerical	Number of floors, primary and secondary function of building (residential, commercial)	
Mobile/Web – 1 numerical selection	Timing of change occurrence (when did land use or building usage change)	
Web - digitization	Shape of change land use, for instance building digitization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV – non-overlapping and no splinter polygons
Mobile - photos	4 photos in cardinal directions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PP – blurry out faces and car plate signs (sections 3.2 and 0) • PI – ensure proper illumination (section 3.2)
Mobile – GPS position	x/y coordinates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PO – GPS accuracy (section 3.3)
login	Login to LandSense federation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UP - User privacy (section 0)

2.4 Serbia - CropSupport

The objective of the INOSENS-led pilot on agricultural land use is to promote citizen-science based approaches to support farming management systems in the Vojvodina province of Serbia. An online platform is linked to photos and data captured in the field by farmers and related farmer networks. The functionalities

offer to describe the crop rotation of a farmer's fields regarding, tillage and other relevant factors. LandSense intends to provide contributing farmers in return EO-based insights about the development of their crops. Subsection 2.4.1 provides a schematic overview and DCR applicability of the pilot. Subsection 2.5.2 provides details on existing requirements relevant to the pilot DCR expressed by stakeholders and identified through literature. Subsection 0 provides an overview of the data collected and shows their link to the DCR of the pilot.

2.4.1 Pilot schematic outline and DCR applicability

Opportunistic campaigns are implemented to collect data via both a mobile and web application. Data collection is complete when procedures provided on both devices are fulfilled. Three data collection requirements apply coupled with quality constraints realized in real and near-real time and two additional post-processing quality check procedures apply. First, as a position accuracy constraint, the data must be captured with a minimum position accuracy of 20m, hence data collection is restricted until necessary GPS accuracy is achieved. Feedback regarding the positional accuracy constraint is provided in real time to the contributor. Second, a photo of the field is captured and images containing faces and car license plates are blurred in NRT by communication with a LandSense service to preserve privacy of the public. Image brightness is checked alongside to ensure appropriate illumination. Contributors add four crop types, which are checked via thematic accuracy assessment post-campaign. Field data collection follows mandatory web digitization of the field by drawing a polygon using either Google imagery as a background or Sentinel 2 data. Timeliness of most recent EO data as background is important as fields change over time and EO imagery is required at least from the same season. Here, the third data collection requirement applies dissolving overlapping polygons and sliver polygons. Users drawing overlapping polygons are prompted to redraw the node that produced the conflict. Field data captured in the proximity (<20m) of the drawn polygon must be dragged and dropped towards it. Contributors then provide inputs for various farm activities (crop related), which are subject to post-campaign thematic accuracy assessment. Timing of vegetation activity such as a fruit onset is provided by linking a date to the activity, checked post-campaign by the assessment of timing.

- Photo privacy validity (PP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and photo analysis 3.2. It is related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

Photos of agricultural land are unlikely to contain faces of people or car license plates, nevertheless the check must be performed

- Photo illumination validity (PI) is an rDCR ensuring interpretation of captured photos (section 3.2) and is related to the purpose axiom to ensure meaning full interpretation of the photo.

Identification of the respective agricultural land use or fruit requires appropriate image lightning. Ideally the captured photo shall allow interpretation of tiling, crop occupation and season.

- Position validity (PO) is a recommended DCR (rDCR) providing estimates of position accuracy of user contributions (section 3.3) and related to the purpose axiom because it allows meaningful interpretation of the data.

Currently the user must achieve a GPS accuracy of 20m. Because agricultural lands of the pilot is usually not or only sparsely covered by vegetation and no major urban infrastructure is found in proximity of the pilot sites GPS accuracy of 20m is achieved rapidly. The 20m GPS accuracy constrain relates to the later linking of GPS information and parcel digitization. Unconstrained GPS accuracy may result in parcel misregistration.

- Polygon validity (PV) is a recommended DCR (rDCR) (section 3.1) and is related to the purpose axiom ensuring that covered areas can be derived correctly. It is also related to the scaling axiom because polygons free of overlaps and splinters can be compared to others and can find conflation in other CO or OSM data bases.

CropSupport provides digitizing capabilities in a web application to map parcels where ground truth was captured using the mobile device. Within the web application digitized parcels must be at least within 25m proximity of the captured ground truth data to successful link both data entries.

- User privacy, time stamp, device details (UP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

This pilot does not collect any additional data about contributors other than those required by the LandSense Federation login

Figure 7 INOSENS pilot data dependencies and flow of data capture to create farm monitoring device

2.4.2 Existing requirements

Climate change increases pressure on farmers to implement timely actions for the optimal management of their farms. Thus far, Serbian farmers base decisions on crop cycles and crop types on experience. An accounting system is required for farmers to undertake bookkeeping of the evolution of their land in a simple web interface that is linked to a mobile application and EO monitoring systems such as Copernicus.

Currently the system offers a platform where users can input current crop fruit, location and related farming activities including timing. During the growing season, different activities can be attached to the field creating a log book/journal. The web-based representation of the information allows easy access, any field can be added and monitored. Thus, enabling comparison against other farmers or among own fields and combination with remote sensing time series analysis. Upscaling is applicable to any location because the pilot is not limited by any constraints.

2.4.3 Data collection catalogue

Table 6 shows data collected for this pilot and the relation to the DCRs. No additional user information other than LandSense login is required. Recording of GPS position in conjunction with entries of field crop types and photos are linked with the web platform. Polygons, drawn in the webform are used as feature entity were the related sources of information find a common container. The online web application also requires entry of dates of activities.

Table 6 Data collection catalogue CropSupport mobile and web application

Collection domain	Categories	DCR and related Quality measure
Mobile – GPS position	x/y coordinates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PO – minimum GPS accuracy $\pm 20m$ (section 3.3)
Mobile - photos	1 to multiple photos of the field investigated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PP – blurry out faces and car plate signs (sections 3.2 and 0) • PI – ensure proper illumination (section 3.2)
Mobile – choice of 4 crop types and varying subcategories	Field crop, vegetable crop, undefined cop type a, undefined crop type b; subtypes (Alfalfa, Corn, Barley, Wheat, Soybean, Potato, Onion, Garlic, Sunflower, White clover, Rapeseed, other field crop, Cabbage, Other Vegetable crops, sugar beet, rye)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NA because of opportunistic campaign design
Web – choice of 5 tillage categories	Ostalo (other), Oranje (Plowing), Zatvaranje zimske brazed (closing winter furrow), Tanjiranj (disking), Razrivanje (?), Kultiviranje (Cultivation),	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NA because of opportunistic campaign design

	Zaoravanje žetvenih ostataka (harvested remains), Formiranje bankova (?)	
Web - digitization	Shape of parcel linked to mobile data captured	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PV – non-overlapping and no splinter polygons (must be in 25m proximity of mobile location)
login	Login to LandSense federation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UP - User privacy (section 0)

2.5 Spain and Indonesia - Natura Alert app

The objective of the Spain and Indonesia pilots led by BLI is to empower volunteers to record threats to biodiversity and changes in specific habitats across protected areas. LandSense provides contributors the Natura Alert mobile application, which allows volunteers and designated IBA caretakers to capture threats which can negatively affect local wildlife populations and habitats. For example, the Indonesia pilot (Flores Island), contributor activities are focused around land change processes, namely recent deforestation. Hence, the pilot relies on a well performing LandSense change detector service. Subsection 2.5.1 provides a schematic overview and DCR applicability of the pilot. Subsection 2.5.2 provides details on existing requirements relevant to the pilot DCR expressed by stakeholders and identified through literature. Subsection 2.5.3 provides an overview of the data collected and shows their link to the DCR of the pilot.

2.5.1 Pilot schematic outline and DCR applicability

Within the map interface of the mobile app, users can mark the location of a threat (i.e. opportunistic) using a pin and then describe the threat using a series of dropdown options. The threat description process follows the global IBA monitoring framework (i.e. assessing and threats based on timing, scope and severity). IBAs worldwide are monitored using simple, standardised methods for recording their state based on identifying various pressures and respective conservation responses that are in place. The threat description follows the current classification scheme from International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) <http://www.iucnredlist.org/technical-documents/classification-schemes/threats-classification-scheme>. Additionally, the app will also feature specific locations (based on satellite imagery analysis) for users to visit to help validate changes/threats on the ground (i.e. guided campaigns).

- Sufficient sampling population (SP) size is a recommended DCR (rDCR) for high confidence thematic accuracy estimates (section 3.4) and to relate to the purpose axiom because it allows meaning full interpretation of the data.

This DCR is connected to the change detection service. For the Indonesia application contributors are sent to locations of recent deforestation occurrence as identified by Sentinel-2 time series analysis. Validity of deforestation occurrence must be checked by LEP QAC. The DCR is only applicable when contribution numbers are high (>500 contributions). That volunteers can follow statistically sound sampling designs which can allow area estimations of the reported threats.

- Sampling stratification (SS) is a rDCR which enables identification of inappropriate contributions (section 3.4) and is related to the scaling axiom because it ensures that the results achieved are comparable for other sites. It is also related to the purpose axiom as it provides a basis to create reliable results worth of decision-oriented interpretation.

BLI's pilots can rely on multiple redundant user contributions to ensure observation validity. This DCR is only applicable when contribution numbers are high (>500 contributions).

- Photo privacy validity (PP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and photo analysis 3.2. It is related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

Although it is unlikely that photos of wildlife or natural threats contain faces and car plate signs the DCR needs to be enforced.

- Photo illumination validity (PI) is an rDCR ensuring interpretation of captured photos (section 3.2) and is related to the purpose axiom to ensure meaning full interpretation of the photo.

Identification of the captured threat requires appropriate image lightning. Ideally the captured photo shall allow interpretation of the treat and allow interpretation of event timing.

- Position validity (PO) is a recommended DCR (rDCR) providing estimates of position accuracy of user contributions (section 3.3) and related to the purpose axiom because it allows meaning full interpretation of the data.

Currently no Natura Alert App specific restrictions apply other than the capture of the GPS coordinates and the location error.

- User privacy, time stamp, device details (UP) is an essential DCR (eDCR) ensuring contributor privacy (section 0) and related to the privacy axiom to ensure users data protection.

This pilot does not collect any additional data about contributors other than those required by the LandSense federation login.

Figure 8 BLI pilot data capture dependencies; * in proximity of guided feature

2.5.2 Existing requirements

Increased pressure on land cover change results in species loss and is a threat to biodiversity. The LandSense change detector service provides spatial explicit information on land cover changes in Indonesia while within Spain Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBA) are demarcated. Existing IBAs in Spain and recent deforestation sites in Indonesia need survey of locals and volunteers to identify existing and emerging threats to biodiversity wildlife. Evidence for the correlation of deforestation and species loss exist, locations of recently deforested sites exist for an accuracy of 85% percent using the highly accurate near real time (NRT) device of the LandSense LEP change detector service. Especially Indonesian sites require engagement of local communities and volunteers to preserve wildlife and safeguard local natural resources. BirdLife’s network of committed volunteers and caretakers will make a difference by reporting biodiversity threats and changes in specific habitats (arid lands, wetlands, grasslands, etc.). The data generated will help to improve BirdLife’s network of Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs) and other key environmentally sensitive regions.

2.5.3 Data collection catalogue

Natura Alert empowers citizens with a tool to send real-time alerts to the Spanish chapter of BirdLife, who could take action if the threat is relevant.

Natura Alert-based collection allows structured real-time reporting of ongoing trends and long-term evolution. A more directed user feedback can be created where volunteers and data analysts of BLI closely

collaborate and create evidence-based results and data sets which can be forwarded to inform the public and decision makers

Upscaling is applicable to any location because the pilot is not limited by any constraints.

Table 7 Data collection catalogue Natura.Alert.app

Collection domain	Categories	DCR and related Quality measure
Mobile – GPS position	x/y coordinates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PO – minimum GPS accuracy $\pm 20m$ (section 3.3)
Mobile - photos	4 photos in cardinal directions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PP – blurry out faces and car plate signs (sections 3.2 and 0) • PI – ensure proper illumination (section 3.2)
Mobile – 5 multiple choice questions	5 multiple choice questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SP - for each class sufficient amount of collected data to calculate confident thematic accuracy (section 3.4) • SS - stratification of samples to cross check users (section 3.5)
login	Login to LandSense federation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UP - User privacy (section 0)

3 Quality items relevant for data collection requirements

This section provides an overview of calculations related to determining the quality of data captured by citizen observations. The described methods in the subsequent sections aim to provide insights into how the QAC within LandSense functions.

3.1 Polygon topology check

Polygon Topology (PV) refer to checks of overlapping polygons and sliver polygons. PT is applicable in web-forms accessed by a desktop or laptop, not via smartphone. The check is done in the backend functionalities of the web application to identify whether a sliver polygon or overlapping polygon is added by a contributor. If an error is recorded the contributor must redraw the respective node to resolve the conflict. This data

collection requirement is used for IGN and INOSENS pilots. The methodology and calculation is based on standard GIS intersect functions.

3.2 Photo analysis

PV is composed of two distinct elements. First, In LandSense pattern recognition is used to identify and blur features that infringe of privacy rights. Image patterns of relevance are human faces and car plate signs. Since the image pattern recognition involves a pre-trained artificial intelligence (AI) it should be deployed on a LandSense server rather than the phone itself. Second, because a lack of brightness or saturation of image content can render the captured photo as obsolete image, metrics are used to judge its quality and may suggest a recapture (e.g. daylight images vs night images) or discard the photo. This service is also deployed on a LandSense server and thus requires communication with the designated phone to provide feedback to the user.

As part of the data quality work provided on the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP), two uses of AI are being developed to perform the following functions:

- Recognise people or faces in an image.
- Recognise car number plates with an aspiration to automatically blur the offending portion of the image.

Both of the procedures utilise TensorFlow (<https://www.tensorflow.org/>) software that employs models of Deep Learning, Machine Learning and Neural Networks. TensorFlow has several in built libraries that can recognise well known objects of interest out of the box via pre-defined models. These are exposed via a REST API defined as a Swagger document (<https://www.openapis.org/>) and made available on the LEP. Additional details of the methodology are described in detail in D5.3.

3.3 Positional accuracy

PA is the degree to which the digital representation of a real-world entity agrees with its true position on the earth's surface (ISO 19157:2013). For LandSense, GPS accuracy and estimated standard error extracted from the contributor's data capture device, in this case a mobile phone. For guided campaigns (i.e. contributor is directed to a point of interest), disparity between point location and contributor location is recorded in addition to standard GPS error. For instance, a GPS standard error of 20m and a disparity of 20m from the point of interest adds up to a total position error of 40m.

3.4 Categorical Accuracy

LandSense accommodates relative and absolute thematic data. Relative thematic data translates to the unique circumstance of UBA's pilot where information about a contributor's subjective perception is collected. Such data cannot be compared against an absolute truth thus an estimate of accuracy, arguably cannot be provided, for instance the mood a subject feels when at a specific location (sub-section 3.3.2). Absolute thematic accuracy relates to a feature objectively shared by everyone, for instance residential land

use is characterized by residential buildings, which are characterized by additional attributes such as maximum number of floors. Thematic accuracy related to simple categories can be computed by dividing correctly classified features against wrongly classified features (e.g. 8/10 = 80% accuracy). Thus, thematic accuracy assessment generally requires a reference data where features are compared against.

LandSense continuous land use or land and cover information or change information requires an accuracy assessment which follows (Olofsson et al., (2014).

BLI, UHEI, INOSENS and IGN are required to:

- correspond at least 85% to reality to be of use for an agency (Anderson et al., 1976)
- accuracies across thematic classes should be similar (Congalton, 1991)
- product should be reproducible
- classification scheme should be applicable across large areas, we recommend usage of Coordination of Information on the Environment (CORINE) as existing quasi standard across EU
- capacity to aggregate classes, season independent legend and usage of vegetation types as indicator for land use, comparability of product to others
- in-situ data (mobile) may support the product
- If required a location may accommodate multiple thematic classes

Consolidated recommendation on map fitness base on simple statistics error matrix (Congalton, 1991) and variate depending on specific application (Olofsson et al., 2014; Stehman et al., 2018). For LandSense we propose conservative consolidated estimation practices as evolved through global observation of forest cover and land cover dynamics (GOFC-GOLD) sourcebook (Arino et al., 2012). Our proposed validation strategy by sample based reference data (Strahler et al., 2006) consisting of sampling design (Foody, 2009), response design (Cohen et al., 2010) and analysis (Card, 1982) were considered to satisfy current good practices (Olofsson et al., 2014). Since LandSense is not strictly a scientific project, case specific modifications are required to accommodate site-specific properties by individual regulations yet following the spirit of aforementioned principles or in other words scientific practice as good as possible.

Sampling design

Sampling design requires a sampling population that enables estimation of accuracy confidence, and satisfies basic statistical principles. Equation 1 (Foody, 2009) suggest sampling population determination for the accuracy assessment:

$$n = \frac{z_{\alpha}^2 P(1-P)}{h^2} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the sample size, h the half width of the desired confidence interval (here, h = 0.01), P the respective class proportion of the classification and $\frac{z_{\alpha}}{2}$ (here, $\alpha = 0.05$) the critical level of the desired significance level. Design-based sampling population determination and random stratification of its elements

does not necessarily provide sufficient substance to create narrow accuracy confidence interval, additional sampling may be required once first accuracy estimates were calculated. When sampling size is determined, opportunistic distribution of sampling points should be avoided in favour of random stratification per land cover or feature. Methods for random stratification of sampling populations are implemented in existing open validation platforms such as laco-wiki.net.

Response design

Response design determines the way how reference data is captured. In general, data valid for response of reality must be superior compared to data used to generate the map (features) in the first place. When observing current evolution of land use or cover, Sentinel 2 data is a particularly suitable source as it provides timely observations with reasonable resolution (10m) and is implemented in laco-wiki.net. Additionally, TimeSync uses time series chips of EO data to determine change occurrence (Cohen et al., 2010) and is an accepted method for assessment of land changes. It is recognized and consolidated within the scientific community (Zhu, 2017), implementations are easily accessible in generic format <http://timesync.forestry.oregonstate.edu/> and for the R environment <https://github.com/bendv/timeSyncR/blob/master/man/tsChipsRGB.Rd>. However, an implementation for Sentinel 2 does not yet exist.

Analysis

The difference between reference data and the map (Congalton, 1991) is the accuracy of the map. Overall accuracy (O), producer's accuracy (P_j), omission error (1 - P_j) expressing the underestimation of a class, user's accuracy (U_i), and commission error (1 - U_i) expressing overestimation of a class, were calculated and reported.

With q being the number of classes and p_{ij} the convolution matrix of class proportions of map and references, overall accuracy is calculated:

$$O = \sum_{j=1}^q p_{jj} \quad (2)$$

Class accuracies from user's and producer's perspectives are calculated for each class according to:

$$U_i = p_{ii}/p_{i+} \quad (3)$$

$$P_j = p_{jj}/p_{+j} \quad (4)$$

According to best practices provided by (Olofsson et al., 2014), accuracy estimates require correction for true marginal map proportions (Card, 1982), by substituting p_{ij} by \hat{p}_{ij} correcting for class proportions as matched by the reference data and its samples n, where W_i was the estimated proportion for a class i.

$$\hat{p}_{ij} = W_i \frac{n_{ij}}{n_{i+}} \quad (5)$$

Matrix \hat{p}_{ij} , corrected for true marginal map proportions. Accuracy standard errors were calculated based on marginal map proportions following (Card, 1982). For overall accuracy, the variance estimate was:

$$\hat{V}(\hat{O}) = \sum_{i=1}^q W_i^2 \hat{U}_i (1 - \hat{U}_i) / (n_{i+} - 1) \quad (6)$$

For class map class i user accuracy variance estimate is calculated:

$$\hat{V}(\hat{U}_i) = \hat{U}_i(1 - \hat{U}_i)/(n_{i+} - 1) \quad (7)$$

Where reference class is j , producer accuracy variance estimate is calculated:

$$\hat{V}(\hat{P}_j) = \frac{1}{\hat{N}_{j+}^2} \left[\frac{N_{j+}^2(1-\hat{P}_j)^2 \hat{U}_j(1-\hat{U}_j)}{n_{j+}-1} + \hat{P}_j^2 \sum_{i \neq j}^q \hat{N}_{i+}^2 \frac{n_{ij}}{n_{i+}} \left(1 - \frac{n_{ij}}{n_{i+}}\right) / (n_{i+} - 1) \right] \quad (8)$$

Above equations relate to figure 1.

		j				
		1	2	...	j	
i	1	n_{11}	n_{12}	...	n_{1j}	n_{1+}
	2	n_{21}	n_{22}		n_{2j}	n_{2+}
	⋮	⋮				
	i	n_{i1}	n_{i2}		n_{ij}	n_{i+}
		n_{+1}	n_{+2}		n_{+j}	n

Figure 9 example of standard confusion matrix where j represents reference data and j the map

Example

Because spatial thematic accuracy assessment can be non-intuitive a detailed example was provided here. In summary of above formulas and explanations: the confidence interval of measured class accuracy determines value of estimated accuracy. Figure 10 provides an example of a UHEI pilot validation mapathon result where initially 1482 reference points were collected to validate a map shown in Figure 11. To satisfy mapping requirements an additional 450 points had to be used and validated in an additional campaign.

Initial sampling population was determined by formula 1. For class 11 (urban fabric) a user accuracy of 73.1% and a confidence interval of 5.07% was estimated using 242 samples. Even in best circumstances map accuracy would be higher than the 70% currently stated by the municipality but lower than LandSense ambition of 85% > 78.17% (73.1% + 5.07%). The producer's accuracy of the same class is centred at 87.9% ranging from 83.75% to 95.05%, thus suggesting additional sampling to satisfy data collection requirements. To make sure the thematic class 11 and its spatial entities in Heidelberg is of value for the local municipality two steps were required:

- Suppression of the commission error of the class (improve the product), identified by low user's accuracy
- Additional sampling points to narrow confidence interval of producer accuracy, identified by producer's accuracy confidence interval

As a result, the map was improved by reviewing OSM land use tags and EO classification and an additional 150 samples was spread into the class to narrow confidence interval. Acknowledging data collection requirements to fit the purpose of municipality requirements lifted the user's accuracy 91.3% ± 3.29% and narrowed producer's accuracy confidence 88.9% ± 3.08%.

Subsequently each class accuracy provided by the initial validation campaign was checked if additional data collection requirements apply to identify a class specific suitability of municipality usage. Class 12 (Industrial, commercial and transport units) required additional sampling to narrow down confidence interval and user accuracy and an improved classification. Class 13 (Mine, dump and construction sites) was considered as unsuitable because of low accuracy and generally high uncertainties same as class 14 (Artificial non-agricultural vegetated areas). Classes 20 (Agriculture areas) and 30 (Forest and seminatural areas) were characterized by satisfactory accuracies and narrow confidence interval suggesting that class specific accuracy is well above 85%. Class 50 (water bodies) also required additional collection of reference points to narrow confidence interval.

Figure 10 example of required data collection for UHEI pilot and its impact on class usage, bars show class specific accuracies (ua = user's accuracy and pa = producer's accuracy) along with confidence interval, black bars relates to initial sampling campaign (1482 points) and grey bars to additional support sampling (450 points added) to meet data collection requirement (decisive identification of accuracy 85%, marked by horizontal dotted green line)

Figure 11 map related to figure 2 which initially sampled by 1482 reference points interpreted by contributors during validation campaign

TI determines the temporal accuracy indicated by the accuracy of a time measurement. For instance, a land cover transformation of forest to agriculture occurred through 2017 but was detected in 2018, thus temporal accuracy of timing is 1 year. Timing of events can be difficult to evaluate as they are only few means to go back in time. Data collection requirement for timing of events such as changes in land use manifested through changes in land cover (UHEI), crop cycle changes (INOSENS) or forest loss or regrowth onset (BLI) for Flores Island, Indonesia p can be captured through the TimeSync method (Cohen et al., 2010). TimeSync makes use of the strategically gathered acquisition of Landsat or Sentinel 2 data and in contrast to commercial missions provides a regular update of any location back to the 1980. Figure 12 shows the functioning of TimeSync and outlines a series of Landsat based time series chips. For LandSense project the temporal domain from September 2016 onwards is of relevance (not shown in the figure) as it marks the project start. Sampling design can be extracted from the previous section (Foody, 2009) alongside with the good practices (Olofsson et al., 2014) for accuracy assessment.

Application is necessary to determine validity of detected forest changes in BLI pilot Indonesia, for valid land use transitions for UHEI pilot and for transitions of crop cycles for INOSENS pilot.

Figure 12 Examples for timesync method where a disturbance event is shown, majority of time series chips before 1994 day 205 show intact forest while from 1995 ay 208 a clear cut is visible note the cloud visible for 1999 day 219 (Cohen et al., 2010)

3.5 Contributors Agreement

We term the interpretation of the same feature by multiple different contributors: redundant interpretation. Guided campaigns offer the opportunity of cross-checking user performance and provide a performance estimate for each data entry. To apply contributor agreement, a subset of 10% of the total population of reference points is checked by 5 contributors simultaneously.

CA is a simple measure scalable to specific features captured from the pilot's studies. Aggregation of multiple user responses into a single measure is an analysis of agreement. Conformity among users can be identified and agreement inconsistencies highlighted. We propose a random sample based re-evaluation scheme to minimize expert involvement and thus cost for quality estimation. LandSense campaigns require revisit and re-interpretation of dedicated fractions of citizen observed features through an evaluation chain. First, an initial fraction of 50% of observed features requires blind re-interpretation by at least another contributor. Second, from the initial two-fold contributor feature evaluation again 50% of features must be re-evaluated by a third citizen and so forth. This blind revisit chain is to be propagated until a fraction of features from the total population exist which was evaluated by at least seven contributors (note: depending on the amount of contributions larger revisit iterations are recommended). Thus, campaign planning should accommodate this scheme when possible to allow observation redundancy. Third, a fraction of 10% of the seven fold re-

evaluated features requires evaluation by a LandSense expert as the necessary absolute measure of reality. Scott's Pi provides a standard measure of agreement ranging across a scale from multiple input sources (Fleiss, 1971). Pi is the proportion of agreeing pairs of classifications from all possible assignments and is calculated:

$$P_i = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} * \sum_{j=1}^k n_{ij}^2 - n_{ij} \quad (9)$$

Where n is the number of ratings per feature and k the number of classes (categories) or in other words choices of users for the specific feature at hand. n_{ij} is the number of users assigned to the i/th task for the j/th class (category). Majority agreement is a common method to aggregate multiple results into a single answer and does ignore existing human skew especially when emotions get involved (Rosling et al., 2018; UN, 2017). LandSense expert's evaluation provides reference to agreement patterns. Successful agreement patterns are of high quality opposite is true for citizen agreement patterns in conflict to the expert. Expert estimation is propagated backwards (statistically or by machine learning) to allow estimation of reference points down the revisit chain. Identification of user performance is a side effect of expert involvement additional allowing a potential user performance weighting scheme.

Figure 13 example for contributor agreement

User privacy licensing and security

D3.1 and D3.2 described that the LandSense project operates an OpenID Connect compliant Oauth2 LandSense Authorization Server (LS AS) which is a collector and processor of personal information for registered applications and services. Applications or services registered with the LS AS require specification of the required personal information. Four data collection and processing levels (scopes) are defined:

- *anonymous*: User is authenticated with the LS AS without any identifier or personal information about the user, or in other words: the user acts as an authenticated anonymous user.
- *cryptoname*: User is identified via a unique identifier (LandSense UUID) generated by the LS AS via a cryptographic hash of the user's identifier received from the identity provider (IP). Any application or service registered as such cannot request personal information from the LS AS via the UUID.
- *profile*: User is identified via the UUID and an application or service can request personal information as specified by OpenID Connect for scope 'profile' via an active Oauth2 access token released by the LS AS
- *email*: User is identified via the UUID and an application or service can request the user's email via an active Oauth2 access token released by the LS AS

By offering these levels of personal information processing, LandSense applications can choose not to receive personal information from contributors (anonymous and cryptoname). When registering with profile or email level, the application or service requires GDPR compliance for collecting and processing of the involved personal information. Once a user interacts with an application registered via level profile or email, it is possible that personal information is processed as outlined in the application's Privacy Statement. When registering the application or service with the LS AS, it is mandatory to provide a Privacy Statement and Terms of Use.

LandSense campaigns are required to choose one of the four levels when registering applications and services that are to be leveraged during the campaign.

3.6 GDPR compliance

GDPR compliancy is required if LandSense captures data linked to persons (levels profile and e-mail as described in the previous section). GDPR provides a legal framework to regulate and guide the design of interconnected CO projects across members of the EU including aspects of privacy for data collected by citizen observatories. Additional licensing aspects, exchange, processing and collecting principles of personal information are provided. This includes acknowledging the data minimization principle, or in other words: only as much personal information as necessary for an application or service shall be collected and processed. GDPR compliance is only necessary if LandSense applications require the collection of personalized data.

3.6.1 Non-GDPR compliance

Confidentiality of collected data is of prime importance in LandSense, hence we recommend usage of unique user ID (UUID) for application and services involving citizen contributions.

We recommend that any application or service stores the LandSense UUID (user's crypto-name) along with collected data. As a result, LandSense services that do not require personal information can process the collected data without compliance to the GDPR. For instance, as done by geo-fencing or data clustering.

Any captured citizen observations dataset requires a creative commons (CC) license. The LandSense Licensing Ontology was developed to derive the following licensing questions based on CC license instances:

- 1) I have two different datasets (a bag of collected data) with two associated licenses. Am I allowed to process the data sets based on the licenses involved? And, if yes, which CC license may the conflated product have?
- 2) I have one or multiple existing data set(s) and like to run a campaign to produce additional data for conflation (create a derivative product). The conflation of the existing data set(s) and the one to be created via a campaign shall have a particular CC license associated. Which CC license, in case there is one, must I apply to the campaign? If multiple licenses are available to choose from, which is the least / most restrictive?

Each LandSense application and service must specify its specific CC license. The LEP provides a page that helps to create a CC license. The license is applied to the collected data and for the result of a service.

3.6.2 Requirements towards data security

Preferably, all information collected in the LandSense CO is publicly accessible. Restrictive access policies require further specification by the LandSense campaign manager regarding access to collected data when designing and running a campaign. The OASIS eXtensible Access Control Markup Language (XACML) or the OGC's geospatial extension Geospatial XACML (GeoXACML) standards provide a framework for creating and enforcing such policies. GeoXACML v1 extends the XACML v2 to derive authorization decisions also based on geographic conditions. As a result LandSense Campaigner should be linked with a XACML or GeoXACML Policy Editor Application (PAP in the figure below) to craft policies that reflect the access conditions to the collected data.

Figure: XACML v2 informative architecture and information flow [XACML v2, fig. 1]

The figure above illustrates the XACML v2 standard compliant flow of information to manage and enforce access restrictions to resources, adopted to use geographic access conditions. In the example above, the user Joe wants to view item #123 that is located at 48°N / 11°E. The policy in place might restrict access to resources at that location because they are located in a protected heritage park. This restriction could be encoded in GeoXACML via the topological function 'within' and the administrative boundaries of the park.

The user's client sends a request to the resource which is intercepted by the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) which consults the GeoXACML Policy Decision Point (GeoPDP) for an authorization decision. The Context Handler (CH) and the Policy Information Point (PIP) get involved to fetch attributes required for deriving a decision. The administration of policies is a separate activity by the policy admin involving the Policy Administration Point (PAP).

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